

IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF THE USE OF MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract: the role and importance of the information and communication technology sector, which includes the production of computer and telecommunication technologies, software products and the provision of a wide range of interactive services on their basis, is growing in Uzbekistan in terms of improving the effectiveness of economic reforms.

Information technology is perfectly connected with information systems, for which information technology is the main environment. In one view, the concept of Information Technology and system seems to be similar, and in fact it is not. Information technology is the process of performing action and steps, guided by the rules that are sorted over the data stored on the computer.

Keywords: pedagogy, information technology, pedagogical skills, quality of Education, Educational efficiency.

ВАЖНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ

Аннотация: В Узбекистане в целях повышения эффективности экономических реформ возрастает роль и значение сферы информационно-коммуникационных технологий, включающей производство компьютерных и телекоммуникационных технологий, программных продуктов и оказание на их основе широкого спектра интерактивных услуг.

Информационные технологии прекрасно связаны с информационными системами, для которых информационные технологии являются основной средой. На первый взгляд понятие информационная технология и система кажутся похожими, но на самом деле это не так. Информационные технологии-это процесс выполнения действий и шагов, которые выполняются на основе правил, упорядоченных по данным, хранящимся в компьютере.

Ключевые слова: педагогика, информационные технологии, педагогическое мастерство, качество образования, эффективность обучения.

INTRODUCTION

Educational-professional programs are laid on the basis of teaching, which are made up of five block-model principles: socio-economic and humanitarian Sciences, Mathematical and natural-scientific Sciences, universal sciences, specialty Sciences, as well as a system of additional Sciences. Technologically, it is directly related to the cultural approach to the choice of content, methods and methodology of professional education.

In the development of these programs, it is noticeable that the task of each block, the interaction between the blocks, is carried out in cooperation with organizational, didactic-technological work and qualified specialists.

If the professional skill program of an educator is considered practical, then the priority will be his integral quality – the skill of the teacher. Despite the fact that there are so many definitions of pedagogical skill, some aspect of skill is definitely expressed in them.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Skill is the art of upbringing and teaching, which is high and constantly rising. An educator is a master of his work, a deep connoisseur of his own science, a good acquaintance with the corresponding fields of Science and art, a good understanding of general and youth psychology in practice, a comprehensive connoisseur of teaching and educational methodology, and a specialist with a high culture.

In pedagogical theory, there are two types of understanding of teacher skills. The first is a connection with the understanding of pedagogical labor, while the second plays a key role in upbringing in the personality of an educator.

It is a fact that does not require proof that the power that makes the country powerful, the nation great is science, education and upbringing. Today, the reforms carried out in our country are aimed at expanding the coverage of young people with higher education, educating them in knowledge and competency, training specialists suitable for World Development.

It is known that information and communication technologies are associated with discoveries in the fields of microelectronics, computational techniques (hardware tools and software), electrology and antoelectronics-microprocessors, semiconductors and fiber-optic cables.

These discoveries allow the development and storage of vast information and their rapid dissemination through communication networks. Connecting computers together and configuring them to communicate with each other allows a new powerful technological system to create network information systems that use a common protocol. They unite people, their homes and offices and develop and complete a huge number of assignments in a very short time. This radically changes the nature of the use of information and the structure of communication. At the same time, computer networks make it possible to communicate with all points of the globe. For the educational system, this creates new opportunities for communication between teachers and students.

It is no coincidence that attention to science has reached a high peak in New Uzbekistan. Because now modern life cannot be imagined without the advancement of Science and education. The development of education in leading countries of the world is also designated as the first priority. After all, the future prosperity of the country is closely related to the achievements it has achieved in this area.

Man is going through the stage of development of development. The progress of Science and technology is the most intense process to date. We know that preschool education and school education, the higher and secondary special education system and scientific and cultural institutions are four continuous rings of the future Renaissance. We consider our kindergarten educator, school teacher, professors and scientific and creative intellectuals to be the four pillars of the New Renaissance[1.]. That is why the goal of the National Training Program is also – to radically reform the educational sphere, to create a national system of highly qualified training at the level of developed democratic states, meeting high moral and ethical requirements. The training of specialists who look at the world with a new Eye, know the eye of work, build and raise the foundations of our great future, is the most important and responsible task facing the educators of our republic.

The main purpose of information technology is to provide the user with the necessary information by processing primary information as a result of targeted action. The information system consists of computers, a network of Computers, Software Products, a database, human

beings, various technical and software communication tools, and environments made up of other devices. The main purpose of the information system is to store and transmit information. Information System Information Processing is a human-computer system.

The state policy of our country in the field of informatization is aimed at creating a national Information System, taking into account the modern world principles of development and improvement of Information Resources, Information Technology and Information Systems. It should be noted that the National Information System includes state bodies, as well as legal entities and individuals, network and territorial information systems. The information system, on the other hand, is the Total Information Resources, Information Technology and communication tools that allow the collection, storage, search, processing and use of information, organized in an organizational way. Information in electronic form within the Information System, the data bank, the database constitute the information resources[2.6.]

When it comes to the work carried out to improve the quality of education, we liken the teaching process to the bridge of goodness, from which we consider it the task of the teacher, that is, teachers, to bring our students from a well-educated, wide-world view. The theoretical and practical part of the lessons is conducted in small groups, using effective methods of pedagogical technology to increase the interest of students.

Currently, in modern society, the dynamics of scientific and technical progress and socio-economic changes are more and more clearly manifested. And the reason for this is expressed in the fact that due to the pandemic, all areas have switched to remote operation mode. The process of such work is considered economically and educationally relevant. Thus, universal informatization, digitization of all spheres of human life, robotization and the creation of artificial intelligence, on the one hand, ensures a sharp decrease in the habit of human activity, and on the other hand, reproductive professions, competencies and functions lead to depreciation in the labor market [3.21]. This means that for everyone, the modern educational system must always create forms and methods for the comprehensive and effective development of its abilities and competencies, which gives it an advantage and competitiveness not only with other people, but also in comparison with artificial intelligence, technology and other opportunities.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The task is to increase the quality of education, the level of spiritual and ideological education. The implementation of the National Training Program should be based on unconditionally new information technologies. Without encouraging the education system, civil society cannot be built. The educational system should consist of a continuous process, not a static system of closed points of view, views. To guarantee the development of our independent republic, the educational system must be dynamic, perfect.

The humanitarian education system is a continuous process of re-realizing personal thinking, developing new curricula, constant exchange of ideas. Currently, in the era of computer networks, the features of the creation and distribution of new technologies are changing, and this is happening in the following areas: firstly, in the modern global market, which is characterized by high competition, skills are of greater importance than ever. Technology transfer and distribution is a very complex process. Secondly, the development of new global norms reflecting the recognition of the value of technologies is also becoming of great importance.

The role of innovative technologies in organizing the educational process of higher education is increasing every day. The use of distance technology has further expanded the

possibilities of modern education. Today it is possible to get an education from anywhere in the Earth's land, taking advantage of the possibility of modern information and communication technologies (ICT). Although Zero traditional education maintains its position, distance learning technologies are gaining popularity day by day in later times.

Today, an educational system is being built in our country aimed at integrating into the new world information and educational environment. This is observed by significant changes in the organization of the educational process that meet modern technical capabilities. The penetration of modern information technologies into the educational sphere makes it possible to qualitatively facilitate and change the forms of Organization of educational methods and the teaching process on the basis of a new approach. Information and communication technologies are the most important part of the process of modernizing the educational system. ICT is information processing methods with various technical and software devices. It is primarily computers with the necessary software and telecommunications tools where data is hosted.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the introduction of systems based on the principles improved in all branches of educational institutions causes an increase in intellectual potential in student-youth.

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